

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

EFFECTIVE USE OF NEW INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract

This article discusses the use of new technology in English lessons to increase students' knowledge and form their cognitive attitudes. The use of new technology ensures that all students perform and learn several exercises in a small amount of time.

Keywords: New technology, information and communication technology, technology, Internet.

Currently, the development of science requires the use of pedagogical technologies, as pedagogical technologies contribute to the development and increase the activity of each student in the learning process. Using new technologies, we create conditions for students to achieve high performance during classes and use advanced knowledge in practice. Use of new technologies (interactive whiteboard, slide, presentation) promotes better mastery of students.

In Kazakhstan, the main goal is the use of new information technologies in education. It is not only a technical means, but also new information, communication technologies and a new method of teaching in the education system.

In the Message of the Head of the state to the people of Kazakhstan it was noted that to meet the needs of information society in the XXI century it is necessary to solve the following problems in the sphere of education: demonstrate the quality of education through the effective use of computer technology, Internet, telecommunications network, electronic and telecommunications facilities, multimedia electronic textbooks in the educational process. In addition, our educated, intelligent generation, can provide us with a bright future. Also, young people who are fluent in several languages, including English, can represent their country, people and culture abroad. [1] Computer Telecommunications are widely used in modern society. For example, in business, information, science and education.

According to modern requirements, every specialist should be a profound expert in his subject, as well as an information competent specialist with historical-cognitive, pedagogical-psychological literacy, political-economic knowledge and information-communication knowledge and a comprehensive knowledge of information and communication technologies.

English, as we know, is the key to modernity, and the key to technology is the computer. English is a great literary language. This language was spoken by the world famous William Shakespeare, Jonathan Swift, Walter Scott.

Undoubtedly, a new telecommunication tool is developing in our state. Modern educators know that the

use of computer and multimedia is a very effective approach to the course of lessons. The power of this tool is so great that with it, a new ideology of world thinking has been introduced into the system of knowledge along with new methods. Computer and information technology-demand of the times.

The main goal of this work is the effective use of the computer network and multimedia - electronic means at foreign language lessons, in particular, the in-depth use of presentations in English lessons and multimedia - electronic means in the walls of the school and in the educational process.[2]

The joint use of presentations with an interactive whiteboard especially increases the interest of students in the classroom. When using the computer, multimedia and electronic textbooks and the interactive whiteboard in English lessons:

teaches reading vocabulary;

rhythm of speech;

dialogues, monologues, and role-playing;

teaches how to write letters;

helps students memorize by explaining grammatical structures.[3]

Nowadays, mastering the English language by computer, telecommunication means takes time itself, and even in the years to come their role will increase.

I consider it necessary and I use them in my lessons to increase students' interest in the subject of English, to master new information technologies, various methods and techniques.

The expected results of using new information tools in English lessons:

helps students with low achievement;

increases the interest of students in the lessons;

increases the number of visuals used in the classroom

increases student creativity;

trains students to work individually;

helps students understand grammatical structures more easily;

develops students' memory, hearing, vision, speech, and thinking;

increases opportunities for discussion and analysis;[4]

I use the computer most often in English discipline when explaining a new lesson, when going through grammatical structures, and in the final lesson.

The main goal of teaching a foreign language - mastering students at the basic level of communication in a foreign language. Accordingly, the content of training includes language, vocabulary, socio-cultural knowledge, abilities and skills to ensure the formation of elementary communicative skills, the ability to apply in the process of mutual cultural communication orally and in writing (word, listening, reading, writing) in the necessary conditions.[5]

Knowledge of a foreign language has become a pressing problem of life. Therefore, in teaching the younger generation a foreign language, there is a need to transform, complicate the various methodological techniques. Of course, in mastering a language still a lot of difficulties. One of them is the speech action. As we know, the main goal of mastering a foreign language-development of communicative communication. The basis of language acquisition is the development of auditory, visual communication through various exercises, the formation of skills of individual work with the student. That is the way of personality formation. The formation of personality in teaching a foreign language is based on a humanitarian orientation. This is the basis of the principle: in teaching the first main node is the student, and the teacher is not only a teacher - he is the developer of cognitive activity. The student is often confronted with psychological difficulties more often than with a real problem. For this reason, they are often silent. That is, the student is silent because he cannot find auxiliary words, linguistic means to express his thoughts, is silent because he is constricted to speak in front of the teacher and the group, is silent because he does not want to show his degree of knowledge.

In such a situation, it is necessary, without putting pressure on the student, to create a comfortable, favorable opportunity for speech, to teach the student to be able to listen to his actions. The teacher must first and foremost be able to teach students how to speak, including striving to master language as a means of communication, awakening students' desire and creating a learning atmosphere to build their skills and abilities.

Finally, the use of new information tools in English lessons, is a requirement of the times. In the developing stage of the new Kazakhstan - introduction of new information technologies in the educational process informs us that our future will be the era of technology. I want to say that the modern generation that comes out of the school walls today still does not allow itself to have only one profession throughout its working life. The future requires a willingness on everyone's part to be versatile and to continue to learn throughout their lives. As the English proverb says, "to think globally and act locally" will require us to think big and act adequately. The formation of the future specialist's personality should be a process that provides continuous education, sustainable development of knowledge, content and structure of professional activity.

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